

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC PULSE: DECODING PAKISTAN'S FINANCIAL STABILITY THROUGH TIME

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ABSTRACT

Financial stability and socio-economic factors are closely interconnected in contemporary times. The purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of socioeconomic factors on financial stability in Pakistan from 2003-2023. The analysis is based on the theoretical background of socio-economic variables and financial stability and analyzing secondary data from the World Development Indicators for Pakistan. The independent variables include gross domestic product, inflation, health expenditures and secondary school enrolment, while the dependent variable is financial stability, using a composite index of domestic credits to the private sector as a proxy for financial stability. The study employs descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, unit root test and ARDL regression analysis to analyze the time series data. The analysis reveals moderate financial stability with varying volatility among independent variables. Weak or negligible correlations are observed between financial stability and GDP, health expenditure, inflation, and school enrollment, although GDP is significantly influenced by inflation and education. Unit root tests confirm that most variables become stationary after differencing. The ARDL model shows that GDP positively affects financial stability in both the short and long term, while inflation negatively impacts it. Health expenditure and school enrollment do not have significant long-term effects. The findings underscore the importance of economic growth and inflation control for financial stability, with limited immediate impact from health and education investments. Sustainable economic policies are essential to enhance financial resilience in Pakistan.

Keywords: Financial stability, inflation, domestic credits to private sectors, gross domestic products, secondary school enrolment.

INTRODUCTION

The global financial crisis of 2007-08 highlighted the importance of financial stability as a key policy concern. Since then, there has been significant debate over whether central banks should take responsibility for financial stability alongside their traditional mandate of controlling inflation. Proponents argue that

financial stability could complement flexible inflation targeting, with central banks using interest rates to address financial imbalances (Woodford, 2012). However, others, such as Svensson (2012), are skeptical and advocate for relying primarily on regulatory tools rather than interest rates to maintain financial stability.

While central banks have long played a role in safeguarding financial stability (Schinasi, 2003), this task is complicated by the fact that financial stability is a public good that may conflict with other policy objectives (Allen and Wood, 2006). Therefore, the rationale for promoting financial stability must be clearly defined to establish accountability and evaluate central bank performance.

In practice, the links between financial stability and central bank policies remain ambiguous and vary across institutions. Unlike the widely agreed-upon goals of price and output stability, financial stability is rarely explicitly defined as a policy objective in central bank mandates (Oosterloo and de Haan, 2004). However, the issue has gained prominence in debates over whether central banks are operating within their legal boundaries. Some argue that if financial stability is a precondition for monetary and macroeconomic stability, an explicit definition may not be necessary for central banks to act within their mandates (Baxter, 2013). Financial stability refers to a condition in which the financial system efficiently allocates resources, assesses and manages risks, and maintains employment levels close to the economy's natural rate. A stable financial system can absorb shocks and continue functioning effectively, even during adverse conditions. It supports economic growth, wealth accumulation, and social prosperity by facilitating credit intermediation and payment services (Rosengren, 2011). Conversely, an unstable system can undermine economic performance. Unlike physical risks such as natural disasters, financial instability can be addressed through policy interventions and regulatory adjustments (Schinasi, 2004).

Schinasi (2004) defines financial stability in terms of the financial system's ability to: (a) facilitate efficient allocation of resources across time and space, (b) assess, price, and manage financial risks, and (c) maintain its core functions even in the face of external shocks or imbalances. Crockett (1997) describes financial stability as the absence of instability, where economic performance is not undermined by asset price fluctuations or institutional failures. Key elements of financial stability include the likelihood of institutional defaults, the scale of losses from defaults, and the interconnectedness

of financial institutions, which can lead to contagion effects. Indicators such as the ratio of regulatory capital to risk-weighted assets and the proportion of nonperforming loans are commonly used to assess financial soundness. However, these metrics often lag behind real-time developments (Čihák and Schaeck, 2010). Excessive credit growth is another critical indicator of financial instability, as rapid credit expansion is strongly associated with banking crises, particularly in emerging markets (Demirgüç-Kunt and Detragiache, 1997; Kaminsky and Reinhart, 1999). While credit growth is easy to measure, determining whether it is excessive remains challenging. Financial stability is fundamental for economic growth, as most transactions in the real economy are conducted through the financial system. (Levine, 2007).

Literature Review

Ijaz (2021) investigates the impact of bank competition on financial stability and economic growth in selected Asian and European economies using techniques like Z-scores, GMM, and non-performing loans. The study finds mixed evidence: while market value approaches support a competition-fragility view, risk-shifting perspectives suggest that competition can enhance stability. It also notes that post-crisis economic and financial linkages have evolved, with emerging markets adopting reforms that yield mixed regulatory outcomes, often balancing or weakening overall stability. Rismana et al. (2021) investigate digital finance's impact on financial stability using data from 120 Indonesian banks (2010–2019). Utilizing univariate linear regression and moderating regression analyses, the study measures indicators such as inflation, growth rate, and the importance of training. It finds that digital finance increases banks' ability to extend credit, thereby enhancing overall credit accessibility; however, its positive effects are reduced when deliberate risk increases and digital payments expand, prompting banks to lower lending to mitigate expected risks, which may lead to liquidity challenges.

Tereseiene et al. (2021) examine sustainable economic growth via the credit transmission channel and financial stability during the COVID-19 pandemic using 2019 data from

European central banks. Employing panel data regression models, they assess credit risk, financial distress, profitability, and solvency. Their results show that although COVID-19 significantly worsened credit risk, financial distress, profitability, and solvency, banks' liquidity improved, indicating sufficient assets to support economic growth despite reduced credit risk-taking.

Ratnawati (2020) explores financial inclusion's impact on economic growth, poverty, income inequality, and financial stability in 10 developing Asian countries (2009–2018) using IMF index data, Z-scores, and dynamic panel models. Measuring financial inclusion by banking access, services, and usage, the study finds significant effects on all four areas. However, the partial effects of financial inclusion are not ideal, indicating that governments must carefully design policies to better leverage financial inclusion for sustainable development.

Ijaz et al. (2019) explored the links between bank competition, financial stability, and economic growth in 38 European countries (2001–2007) using the Boone indicator, Z-score, and GMM model. With variables including bank competition, GDP growth, and return on assets, they found that formal competition arrangements foster economic growth and banking stability, recommending that European banks strengthen competitive strategies. A noted limitation is the use of country-level data, suggesting future research should examine bank-level details (e.g., bank type and domestic versus foreign share) using quintile regression.

Rakshit and Bardhan (2019) examined whether bank competition promotes economic growth in selected South Asian countries (1997–2016) via linear index, panel regression, and GMM models. Incorporating variables such as inflation, marginal cost, government effectiveness, and gross capital formation, they argue that national banks must balance market power and competition to secure financial stability and productivity. They propose flexible regulatory policies to enhance bank contestability, though the study does not capture the full short-run and long-run joint impacts or the causality among competition, stability, and growth.

Sotiropoulou et al. (2019) investigated financial development, stability, and economic growth in the EU (28 countries, 2004–2014) using the

GMM estimator and dynamic panel techniques. Using variables like growth rate, private credit, liquid liabilities, bank assets, market capitalization, and inflation rate, their findings indicate that financial development does not inherently boost economic growth. They suggest policymakers focus less on development per se and more on strengthening the financial system's capacity, especially by addressing non-performing loans that harm growth.

Nasreen and Anwar (2017) used the Human Development Index and Financial Stability Index to analyze how financial stability affects economic development in five South Asian economies (Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India, Nepal, and Bangladesh) from 1980 to 2012. With variables such as GDP per capita and financial vulnerability indicators, they found a significant positive relationship between economic development and financial stability, emphasizing that a sound and stable financial sector is essential for long-term development in South Asia.

Ashraf et al. (2016) investigated whether implementing a Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) enhances banking financial stability. Using data from 948 banks across 85 North American and European countries during 2003–2013 (World Bank macroeconomic data), and employing GMM and Z-score methods, the study supports Basel III guidelines—showing that NSFR positively contributes to bank stability even after controlling for other factors. The authors suggest further research on whether NSFR correlates with lower bank credit risk and its applicability to Islamic banks.

Morgan and Pontines (2014) examined the interplay between financial stability and financial inclusion across 164 economies over 52 years (since 1960) using World Bank global financial data. By analyzing non-performing loans and Z-scores along with indicators such as savings, borrowings, payments, and risk management, they found that increased financial inclusion can boost bank deposits, improve liquidity, and enhance monetary policy transmission, although it may also disrupt credit standards and raise reputational risks. They propose future work on the impact of household inclusion and alternative stability measures.

Ginevičius and Podvezko (2013) assessed the stability and soundness of 8 Lithuanian banks

during 2007–2009 using capital assets, management earnings, and liquidity via Promethean and MCDA methods. Their findings indicate that robust economic development in a bank-based system depends on the stable performance of commercial banks. The study underscores the complexity of evaluating bank stability and calls for enhanced MCDA models to better guide stakeholders.

Hassan et al. (2011) examine the link between financial development and economic growth in 163 developing countries (1980–2007) using a nested panel data structure. They find a positive relationship—especially in non-industrial nations—with bidirectional causality in many regions and a significant role for trade and government consumption. However, a robust financial system alone does not guarantee sustained growth.

Monnin and Jokipii (2010) employ a PVAR model on data from 521 banks in 18 OECD countries (1980–2007) to analyze the effect of banking sector stability—measured by distance to default—on GDP growth. Their results indicate that stable banking sectors significantly drive growth and reduce economic volatility, particularly during unstable periods.

Cihak and Hesse (2008) investigate Islamic banking stability using Z-scores from the Bank Scope Database (1993–2004) across 20 Islamic banking systems. They reveal that smaller Islamic banks tend to be more stable than larger ones, suggesting that risk management challenges increase as bank size grows.

Berger et al. (2008) analyze banking competition and financial stability in 8,274 banks from 30 developed countries (1999–2005) using a GMM estimator. They discuss two views: the “rivalry fragility” view, where increased competition reduces market power and heightens risk, and the “competition stability” view, where banks with market power might offset risks through higher capitalization and other safeguards.

Herrero and Del Rio (2003) study financial stability and monetary policy design in 79 countries (1970–1999) using a binary logit model, focusing on exchange rates, monetary policy, and inflation targeting. Their findings suggest a need to further explore the link between central bank objectives and outcomes, as well as to consider broader definitions of financial stability.

Mande et al. (2020) examine financial stability and income growth in 23 emerging market economies (1996–2018) using a dynamic panel estimator. The study concludes that financial instability—especially stemming from securities market volatility and non-performing loans—significantly hampers income growth, with the securities market channel exerting a somewhat stronger influence than composite instability measures.

Soedarmono et al. (2014) examine bank market power, economic growth, and financial stability in commercial banks across 12 Asian countries (2001–2007). Their econometric analysis finds that higher market power is linked to better capital adequacy; however, increased capitalization in less competitive markets does not sufficiently counteract moral hazard that drives risky behavior. They also note that robust economic growth can mitigate excessive risk-taking, though the lingering effects of the 1997 Asian crisis persist in downturns.

Creel et al. (2014) investigate the relationship between financial stability and economic performance in 27 EU countries (1998–2017) using a GMM estimator with variables like GDP per capita, inflation, and government consumption. Their findings suggest that increased financial depth does not necessarily lead to improved economic outcomes in the Euro zone, challenging the notion that managing financial sector size negatively impacts growth. They call for further research with expanded datasets and a closer look at policy instruments to better address financial instability.

Fouejieu et al. (2012) explore trade-offs between macroeconomic and financial stability using a New Keynesian model with data from Kenya's central bank (2008–2009). Inflation and interest rates impact financial stability, with results showing that central banks addressing financial imbalances may stabilize financial risks but increase price volatility. Their findings highlight potential conflicts in monetary policy goals.

Dhal et al. (2011) investigates financial stability, economic growth, inflation, and monetary policy in India (1996–2013) using a VAR model. Their study finds that financial stability promotes growth and enhances monetary transmission, while inflation negatively affects stability. The results support the integration of financial

stability objectives into macroeconomic policy frameworks.

Theoretical and Conceptual Links

The impact of socio-economic factors on financial stability can be analyzed using the Financial Instability Hypothesis (FIH) and Endogenous Growth Theory. Hyman Minsky's (1992) Financial Instability Hypothesis posits that financial stability is cyclical, driven by interactions between economic agents and financial markets. Economic booms lead to excessive risk-taking, increasing financial fragility and potentially causing instability and crises. In Pakistan, socio-economic factors like income inequality, inflation, and employment levels affect financial stability by influencing borrowing behavior. During growth periods, increased credit availability and speculative investments can offer short-term stability, but excessive debt reliance can cause financial vulnerabilities, especially in a country prone to economic shocks (Minsky, 1992). Inflation, interest rates, and fiscal policies are crucial in determining economic resilience. Pakistan's financial sector has faced instability due to rising inflation and

currency devaluation, consistent with Minsky's view of cyclical financial stability (Khan & Qayyum, 2007). Endogenous Growth Theory, developed by Romer (1986) and Lucas (1988), highlights the importance of human capital, innovation, and policy interventions in sustaining long-term growth. Financial stability is linked to socio-economic conditions like education levels, technological advancements, and supportive government policies. In Pakistan, insufficient human capital investment and weak institutional frameworks limit sustained growth and financial stability (Romer, 1986). The theory examines how factors such as unemployment, poverty, and inequality affect financial stability by restricting market access and reducing consumer confidence. A poorly developed financial sector and inadequate education investment hinder economic development, leading to long-term instability (Nasir & Khalid, 2004). Policymakers in Pakistan should focus on structural reforms to improve financial inclusion and economic resilience, as suggested by endogenous growth models. Based on this theoretical framework, the following conceptual framework is constructed.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Research Methodology

The data type is annual time series secondary data and the data is sourced from WDI (world development indicators). The analysis uses 21 years of data for the period of 2003-2023 and the sample country is Pakistan.

$$FS = f(GDP, INF, HE, SSE)$$

$$FS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \beta_2 INF_t + \beta_3 HE_t + \beta_4 SSE_t + \epsilon_t$$

FS	=	Financial Stability
GDP	=	Gross domestic product
INF	=	Inflation
HE	=	Current Health Expenditures
SSE	=	Secondary school enrolment
β 's	=	coefficients
ϵ	=	error term
t	=	period 2003-2023

Measurement of Variables

The selected variables of our study are shown in the following table 1:

Table 1

Variables	Measurement	Source
Financial Stability	A composite index of Domestic credit provided by the financial sector (% of GDP), Domestic credit to the private sector (% of GDP) and Domestic credit to private sector by banks (% of GDP).	WDI
GDP	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	WDI
Inflation	Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %).	WDI
Health expenditure	Current health expenditure (% of GDP)	WDI
Secondary School Enrolment	School enrollment, secondary (% gross)	WDI

Estimation Techniques

This study employs a combination of econometric techniques to analyze the impact of socioeconomic factors on financial stability in Pakistan. These techniques include descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, unit root tests, the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model, and the VECM (Vector Error Correction Model). These methods capture both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships between the variables.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

Before proceeding with advanced econometric techniques, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis are conducted to summarize the data and identify preliminary relationships between variables. Descriptive Statistics measure the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum. Correlation coefficients are computed to assess linear relationships.

Unit Root Tests

To determine the stationarity of the time series data, unit root tests are performed. Non-stationary data can lead to spurious regression results, so it is essential to check the order of integration of the variables. This study employs the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \sum \delta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Phillips-Perron (PP) Test: A non-parametric alternative to ADF.

ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) Model

The ARDL model examines the long-run and short-run relationships between socioeconomic

factors and financial stability. It is suitable for mixed integration orders and small samples.

- ARDL Model Specification:

$$\Delta FS_t = \alpha_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta FS_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_i \Delta SE_{t-i} + \lambda_1 FS_{t-1} + \lambda_2 SE_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

- Bounds Testing for Cointegration: Tests the null hypothesis of no cointegration.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

If cointegration is confirmed, the VECM is employed to analyze the short-run dynamics and the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium.

- VECM Specification:

$$\Delta FS_t = \alpha_0 + \sum \beta_i \Delta FS_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_i \Delta SE_{t-i} + \theta ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Diagnostic and Stability Tests

To ensure robust results, the following diagnostic tests were conducted: the Jarque-Bera Test for normality of residuals, the Breusch-Godfrey LM Test to detect autocorrelation, and the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests to assess model stability.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Stat

Descriptive statistics are brief descriptive coefficients that summarize a given data set, which can be either a representative of the entire population or a sample of a population. Descriptive statistics are broken down into measures of central tendency and measures of variability.

Table: 2

	FS	GDP	HE	INF	SES
Mean	20.07926	2.058979	2.581341	9.043598	28.89359
Median	18.11353	2.682325	2.551087	9.036335	30.35768
Maximum	27.94574	5.202456	2.952730	25.99977	42.35869
Minimum	13.83730	-3.038893	2.140169	0.922163	0.000000
Std. Dev.	4.112098	2.308686	0.256367	5.420917	11.32120
Skewness	0.558354	-0.500885	-0.127675	1.380450	-1.477923
Kurtosis	2.009572	2.435228	1.714100	5.694377	4.768677
Jarque-Bera	1.949485	1.157196	1.503899	13.02196	10.38209
Probability	0.377289	0.560684	0.471446	0.001487	0.005566
Observations	21	21	21	21	21

Table 2 provides an overview of the intertemporal properties of the data. Financial stability (FS) demonstrates moderate stability with a mean of 20.08, slight right-skewness, a standard deviation of 4.11, and positive skewness. The kurtosis is close to 3, indicating a normal distribution. GDP per capita growth has an average annual growth rate of 2.06%, slight left-skewness, a standard deviation of 2.31, and a flatter distribution, as confirmed by the Jarque-Bera test. Health expenditure as a percentage of GDP averages 2.58%, showing minimal variability, a nearly symmetric distribution, and a flatter-than-normal distribution, as indicated by the Jarque-Bera test. Inflation displays a mean

rate of 9.04%, significant variability, and a right-skewed distribution with high positive skewness and kurtosis. The significant Jarque-Bera test points to non-normality, suggesting periods of severe inflationary pressure. Finally, school enrollment averages 28.89%, indicating low levels with significant variability. The distribution is left-skewed with high kurtosis, confirming non-normality as indicated by the significant Jarque-Bera test.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation is a statistical term describing the degree to which two variables move in coordination with one another.

Table: 3

Variables	FS	GDP	HE	INF	SES
FS	1.000000				
GDP	0.092395	1.000000			
HE	0.000386	-0.143814	1.000000		
INF	-0.160515	-0.630552***	0.049903	1.000000	
SES	-0.004252	0.541544**	-0.136816	-0.417090**	1.000000

***, **, * represent significance level 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Table 3's correlation matrix provides insights into the linear relationships between variables. Financial stability (FS) shows a very weak positive correlation with GDP per capita growth (0.092395) and almost no correlation with health expenditure (0.000386). There is a weak negative correlation between FS and inflation (-0.160515) and a negligible correlation with secondary school enrollment (-0.004252). GDP per capita growth has a weak negative correlation with health expenditure (-0.143814) and a strong negative correlation with inflation (-0.630552*), indicating that higher inflation is linked to lower economic growth. GDP also shows a moderate positive correlation with secondary school enrollment (0.541544), suggesting that higher

enrollment rates are associated with increased economic growth. Health expenditure has a very weak positive correlation with inflation (0.049903) and a weak negative correlation with school enrollment (-0.136816). Inflation shows a moderate negative correlation with secondary school enrollment (-0.417090**), implying higher inflation may reduce access to education. Overall, the correlations suggest that while socio-economic factors may not directly influence financial stability linearly, GDP growth is significantly affected by inflation and benefits from higher school enrollment.

Unit Root Test

The results from the ADF Fisher and Phillips-Perron Fisher Unit Root Tests provide critical

insights into the stationarity of the variables used in the study.

Table: 4

Variable	At Level without Trend	At 1st Difference without Trend	At Level Trend	At 1st Difference Trend
ADF Fisher Unit Root Test				
FS	-0.377318	-3.596807**	-5.090643***	-
GDP	-2.955057*	-4.802178***	-2.972801	-4.65031***
HE	-1.879305	-3.71244**	-2.03208	-3.582714*
INF	-0.318251	-3.190367**	-0.426106	-3.350176*
SES	-2.234317	-8.800849***	-1.666775	-9.017385***
Phillips-Perron Fisher Unit Root Test				
FS	-0.707963	-3.415054**	-2.382677	-3.315945*
GDP	-2.87798**	-8.763964***	-2.919943	-8.320616***
HE	-1.879305	-3.735976	-2.03208	-3.612718
INF	-0.39772	-3.217579**	-0.470794	-3.357076*
SES	-4.625744***	-6.800037***	-4.296559**	-8.643041***

***, **, * represent significance level 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Table 4 presents the results of the unit root test. The results from the ADF Fisher and Phillips-Perron Fisher Unit Root Tests provide critical insights into the stationarity of the variables used in the study. For Financial Stability (FS), the ADF test shows that FS is not stationary at level without trend but becomes stationary at the first difference and level with trend. The Phillips-Perron test confirms this by indicating FS is not stationary at level but becomes stationary at the first difference without a trend and with a trend. GDP per capita growth (GDP) exhibits non-stationarity at level with a trend in the ADF test but becomes stationary at the first difference with and without a trend. The Phillips-Perron

test shows that GDP is stationary at level without trend and becomes even more stationary at the first difference. Health Expenditure (HE) remains non-stationary at level in both tests, but the ADF test suggests it becomes stationary at the first difference, while the Phillips-Perron test shows mixed results. Inflation (INF) is non-stationary at level in both tests but becomes stationary at the first difference with and without trend. School Enrollment (SES) is also non-stationary at level but becomes stationary at the first difference, as indicated by both tests. Overall, the results suggest that differencing the data is necessary to achieve stationarity for most variables, which is essential for reliable econometric analysis.

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Table 4

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-215.3174	NA	8122.611	23.19131	23.43984	23.23337
1	-149.7379	89.74037	126.7392	18.91978	20.41100	19.17215
2	-100.4397	41.51424*	19.92547*	16.36208*	19.09598*	16.82476*

The table 4 evaluates different criteria to determine the optimal lag length for a VAR model, which includes variables like FS, GDP, HE, INF, and SES. The analysis covers data from 2003 to 2023, with 19 observations. Among the

criteria (LogL, LR, FPE, AIC, SC, HQ), Lag 2 is identified as the best choice, indicating it provides the best fit for the model based on all criteria used.

ARDL - Long Run Coefficients

Table 5

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
FS(-1)	1.026769	0.083341	12.32010	0.0000
GDP	0.383844	0.193781	1.980811	0.0676
HE	1.393043	1.309469	1.063823	0.3054
INF	-0.155364	0.078989	-1.966891	0.0693
SES	-0.039168	0.035503	-1.103225	0.2885
C	-2.701594	4.468103	-0.604640	0.5551
R-squared	0.918014	Durbin-Watson stat		2.592734
Adjusted R-squared	0.888733	F-statistic		31.35200
		Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000

Table 5 presents the ARDL regression results, indicating strong persistence in financial stability (FS) in Pakistan, as evidenced by the highly significant lagged FS coefficient. This suggests that past financial stability conditions heavily influence current levels. GDP per capita growth (GDP) has a positive but marginally significant impact on financial stability, while inflation (INF) negatively affects FS, also marginally significant. Health expenditure (HE) and school

enrollment (SES) do not show statistically significant impacts on financial stability. The model demonstrates a strong overall fit, with an R-squared of 0.918, indicating that the independent variables explain approximately 91.8% of the variation in financial stability. The F-statistic confirms the model's overall significance, and the Durbin-Watson statistic suggests that serial correlation is not a major issue.

Bounds Test

Table 6

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	5.359733	4
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Table 6 presents the BOUNDS test results, which reveal a long-term relationship between financial stability (FS) and socioeconomic factors in Pakistan. The F-statistic value of 5.359733 exceeds the upper critical bounds at all significance levels, indicating a rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration. This suggests that GDP per capita growth, inflation,

health expenditure, and secondary school enrollment are significantly related to financial stability over the long term. These results emphasize the importance of sustainable economic policies, investment in healthcare, and education to enhance financial stability in Pakistan.

ARDL Cointegrating Form

Table 7

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GDP)	0.383844	0.193781	1.980811	0.0676
D(HE)	1.393043	1.309469	1.063823	0.3054
D(INF)	-0.155364	0.078989	-1.966891	0.0693
D(SES)	-0.039168	0.035503	-1.103225	0.2885
CointEq(-1)	0.026769	0.083341	0.321195	0.7528

Table 7 provides ARDL cointegration results,

highlighting both short-term dynamics and long-

term relationships between variables. GDP per capita growth (D(GDP)) has a positive short-term impact on financial stability, significant at the 10% level. Inflation (D(INF)) negatively affects financial stability in the short term, also significant at the 10% level. However, health expenditure (D(HE)) and secondary school enrollment (D(SSES)) do not show significant short-term impacts on financial stability. The error correction term (CointEq(-1)) indicates a

slow adjustment back to equilibrium, suggesting that deviations from the long-term equilibrium are not quickly corrected. The BOUNDS test confirms a long-term relationship between financial stability and socio-economic factors. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of understanding socio-economic factors, structural and institutional influences and focusing on long-term strategies for sustainable development to enhance financial stability in Pakistan.

Ramsey Reset Test

Table 8

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.958486	13	0.0720
F-statistic	3.835667	(1, 13)	0.0720

Table 8, the Ramsey RESET test is used to check whether the functional form of the regression model is correctly specified. It detects omitted variable bias or incorrect functional form by introducing higher-order terms of the fitted values into the regression. The p-value of 0.0720 is greater than 0.05 but less than 0.10, suggesting that the test is marginally significant at the 10% level but not at the conventional 5% significance level. Since the null hypothesis of the RESET

test states that the model is correctly specified, we fail to reject the null at the 5% level, meaning there is no strong evidence of misspecification. However, some signs at the 10% level suggest possible functional form issues. Key implications include no strong evidence of model misspecification since the p-value is above 0.05, indicating no strong statistical reason to reject the current model specification.

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Lm Test

Table 9

F-statistic	4.209136	Prob. F (1,13)	0.0609
Obs*R-squared	4.891746	Prob. Chi-Square (1)	0.0270

The table 9, Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test results reveal critical insights into the presence of serial correlation in the residuals of the regression model. The F-statistic value of 4.209136, with a p-value of 0.0609, suggests marginal significance at the 10% level but not at the conventional 5% significance level.

CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares Test

The CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests are also conducted for both the long-run and short-run models. Figure 1 illustrates the results of these stability tests.

The CUSUM test, the cumulative sum of recursive residuals (blue line) stays within the 5% significance boundaries (red dashed lines) throughout the period (approximately periods 10

to 23), indicating parameter stability. Had the blue line crossed the boundaries, it would suggest structural breaks or parameter instability.

The CUSUM of Squares test is more sensitive to sudden parameter changes. The cumulative sum of squared recursive residuals (blue line) shows some upward movement but remains within the 5% significance boundaries, confirming parameter stability over the sample period. The tests indicate stable model parameters, no significant structural breaks, and an adequate model specification for the data analyzed. This stability implies reliable predictions and inferences from the model across the entire sample period.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper investigates the impact of socio-economic factors on financial stability. The findings of this study provide critical insights into the impact of socio-economic factors on financial stability in Pakistan from 2003 to 2023. The descriptive statistics indicate that financial stability exhibits moderate variability, with inflation showing the highest volatility and school enrollment displaying significant dispersion. The correlation analysis highlights weak relationships between financial stability and the independent variables, suggesting that other structural factors may influence financial stability beyond the selected socio-economic indicators. The unit root tests confirm that most variables are non-stationary at level but become stationary at the first difference, necessitating the use of an econometric approach capable of handling mixed order integration. The ARDL model results reveal that financial stability in Pakistan is strongly influenced by past stability conditions, emphasizing its persistent nature. GDP per capita growth has a positive yet marginally significant impact on financial stability, while inflation negatively affects financial stability, reinforcing the destabilizing effect of inflationary pressures. However, health

expenditure and secondary school enrollment do not show significant direct impacts on financial stability, suggesting that their benefits may materialize over a longer horizon rather than in the short term. The BOUNDS test confirms the presence of a long-term relationship between financial stability and the independent variables, highlighting the importance of sustainable economic growth, inflation control, and investment in education and healthcare for long-term financial stability. The ARDL cointegration analysis further supports the short-term impact of GDP growth and inflation on financial stability, while the insignificant error correction term suggests that deviations from equilibrium are not swiftly corrected. These findings underscore the need for well-balanced economic policies that foster sustainable growth, inflation stability, and long-term investments in human capital to enhance financial stability in Pakistan. The findings of this study suggest that policymakers should prioritize strategies that promote sustained economic growth and control inflation to enhance financial stability in Pakistan. Given the strong positive relationship between GDP growth and financial stability, the government should focus on policies that encourage investment, industrial expansion, and job creation. The inflation control mechanisms, such as prudent monetary policies and supply-side interventions, should be implemented to mitigate its destabilizing effects. While the immediate impact of health expenditure and education on financial stability appears limited, long-term investments in these sectors remain crucial. Policymakers should enhance the efficiency of public spending in health and education to foster human capital development, which can indirectly strengthen economic and financial resilience over time. Strengthening financial regulations and improving governance

in the financial sector will also play a vital role in ensuring a stable economic environment.

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